

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ANALYTICS IN GOVERNMENT DECISION-MAKING: A MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH USING COVID-19 VACCINATION TWEETS

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ABSTRACT

Social media has emerged as a vital platform for expressing public opinion and disseminating information. During the COVID-19 pandemic, governments worldwide leveraged social media platforms to inform citizens about policies, preventive measures, and vaccination campaigns. Analyzing these vast amounts of data using machine learning and social media analytics (SMA) provides crucial insights to support policy development and strategic decision-making. This study explores the role of SMA in government decision-making during the COVID-19 pandemic by evaluating sentiment classification on English-language tweets related to vaccination. We created a novel COVID-19 vaccine-related tweet dataset and applied six machine learning algorithms—Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), XGBoost, Decision Tree (DT), Naïve Bayes (NB), and Logistic Regression (LR)—to classify tweet sentiments. Performance metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score were used to compare model performance. The results indicate that the Random Forest model outperformed others, achieving the highest accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. This demonstrates the potential of SMA combined with machine learning in capturing public sentiment and supporting informed government responses during public health crises.

Keywords: *Social Media Analytics, COVID-19 Vaccination, Sentiment Analysis, Machine Learning, Government Decision-Making*

1. INTRODUCTION

Social media's explosive growth has drastically changed how individuals connect with the government and other institutions, communicate, and express their thoughts [1]. The most popular social networking site for extracting information is Twitter. This is because Twitter material is abundant, accessible, and readily available. Every day, millions of tweets are sent on nearly any subject. Thus, social media is turning into a valuable information resource [2]. Twitter has become a vital forum for public conversation among these platforms, where people share their opinions, worries, and support for social causes, legislative reforms, and governmental policies [1]. Social media has developed into an immense repository of public opinion that can be used to make well-informed decisions, with millions of individuals publishing content every day. In

particular, governments have a great chance to assess public opinion, forecast responses, and adjust policy by analyzing social media tweets [1].

In the past, governments used systematic interviews and surveys to gauge popular opinion. Although helpful, these approaches frequently had delays and small sample sizes. In contrast to conventional methods, social media offers large-scale, unfiltered, real-time insights into the opinions and attitudes of the general population. Governments can use tweet analysis to assess public sentiment before enacting new laws or regulations. By taking a proactive attitude, policymakers may boost acceptance rates, lessen public opposition, and make well-informed decisions. By tracking and examining tweets, government organizations may spot new problems, keep track of public complaints, and assess the effects of policies. Using this data-driven approach, authorities may anticipate potential obstacles,

amend legislation, and enhance legislative proposals before initiating new initiatives.

Crisis management is another important area of social media-driven decision-making. Government may use social media posts to evaluate the situation on the ground, identify impacted areas, and distribute resources in response to emergencies like pandemics, natural disasters, or security concerns [3].

To efficiently handle and examine the enormous number of tweets, machine learning methods are required. Machine learning algorithms can use topic modeling, sentiment analysis, and natural language

processing techniques to derive valuable insights from textual data. By dividing tweets into sentiment classes (positive, negative, or neutral), these methods assist policymakers in gauging the public's general response to proposed legislation or administrative measures. To further improve decision-making, machine learning-based categorization algorithms may also identify underlying issues, recurrent themes, and patterns in social media conversations. To improve disaster response operations, machine learning models can identify false information, filter pertinent tweets, and give authorities precise, timely insights [3].

Figure 1: Social Media's Role In Citizen Participation In Governance [4, 5, 6, 7]

Existing research mostly concentrates on qualitative or conventional analytical methodologies, even though social media sites like Facebook and Twitter are becoming increasingly significant in influencing public debate and policy choices. The majority of earlier research focuses on descriptive analysis, uses small datasets, or examines trends on a single platform without scalable, real-time sentiment modeling. Furthermore, not many studies investigate the use of cutting-edge machine learning methods to methodically categorize and evaluate public opinion during significant occurrences like the COVID-19 epidemic. This leads to a major gap in the use of real-time, large-scale public opinion data for evidence-based governance. With the goal of assisting more inclusive, responsive, and data-driven government decision-making, the current study suggests a machine learning-driven sentiment analysis framework utilizing Twitter data pertaining to COVID-19 immunization in order to meet this difficulty.

This study's main goal is to draw attention to how important social media analytics are to government and decision-making. In order to show how governments may use real-time insights to develop more informed and citizen-centric policies, this study will examine how well machine learning approaches analyze social media data. This research

advocates for a data-driven approach to governance that guarantees more openness, inclusion, and responsiveness to close the gap between social media conversation and policy execution. It seeks to offer insightful information to scholars, data scientists, and policymakers who are interested in using technology to enhance governance outcomes.

This research is guided by the following two research questions:

RQ1: How can machine learning techniques be effectively applied to analyze sentiment in Twitter data related to COVID-19 vaccination, and what insights can be derived to support government decision-making?

RQ2: How accurately does sentiment analysis of COVID-19 vaccination-related tweets reflect public opinion, and in what ways can this information inform evidence-based policy decisions?

1.1 Motivation

Social media, particularly Twitter, has emerged as a powerful platform for public discourse, especially during critical events like the COVID-19 pandemic. Governments around the world are increasingly turning to these platforms to understand citizen concerns, sentiments, and responses to public health initiatives. However, a review of existing literature reveals several gaps. Most studies employ traditional qualitative or

statistical methods, such as semantic analysis or logistic regression (Refs. [1], [9], [12], [13], [20]), and often rely on limited, static, or non-representative datasets. Additionally, these works typically analyze general political trends or crisis communication but rarely focus on COVID-19 vaccination-specific sentiment analysis.

Moreover, the studies lack the application of advanced machine learning techniques that can offer automated, real-time, and scalable insights from massive volumes of unstructured data. With governments increasingly seeking data-driven strategies for decision-making, there is a pressing need for a framework that can bridge the gap between public sentiment and timely, evidence-based policy formulation. This study is motivated by the opportunity to leverage Twitter data using machine learning to inform vaccination policies, improve public communication, and ultimately support better governance.

1.2 Novelty of the Study

This study uniquely applies machine learning techniques to analyze sentiment from COVID-19 vaccination-related tweets, offering real-time, scalable insights into public opinion. Unlike previous works that rely on traditional methods or small datasets, this research provides a data-driven framework directly aimed at supporting government decision-making and policy formulation.

This document is structured as follows. The related works are included in Section 2. The data preparation process for machine learning is explained in Section 3. The suggested architecture for sentiment analysis is explained in Section 4. In Section 5, the experiment and analysis of the results are described. The paper's results are summed up in the conclusion section.

2. RELATED WORKS

This section presents a comprehensive analysis of the general approaches, methodologies, and findings from previous studies on the contribution of social media to enhancing public involvement in governmental policy and decision-making.

Ali Sercan Basyurt et al.[8] defined how government organizations may enhance crisis communication by using a social media analytics dashboard. The dashboard helps with crisis management by providing insights into sentiment analysis, public debate, and developing themes.

Immaculate Wanza Musyoka et al. [9] examined the methods for predicting political influence on Twitter using semantic analysis (SA) and social network analysis (SNA). Because of their ease of use and accuracy, supervised machine learning models such as Naïve Bayes and Support Vector Machine are frequently employed. Using a variety of approaches improves performance, and improving political analysis outcomes requires tackling issues like data cleansing, slang, and unstructured language. Abhinav Kumar et al. [3] examined a deep multi-modal neural network that combines tweet text and image data to classify informative Twitter content during emergencies. Using LSTM for text and VGG-16 for pictures, the model performs noticeably better than text-only models, with enhanced F1-scores between 0.74 and 0.93. Olfa Belkahla Driss et al. [1] proposed a framework using Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) to extract insights from social media data for government policy-makers. They emphasize how social media posts may identify important public issues, including public administration, the environment, and road safety, and use that information to guide policy decisions. Prabhsimran Singh et al. [10] proposed a cloud-based system that uses social media analytics to track government initiatives. It was tested using Twitter data about GST and showed how government actions impacted public mood, highlighting the system's usefulness for real-time policy review and involvement. Kayla Schwoere [11] investigated the mobilization of Twitter users in reaction to proposed changes to the FOIA regulations. A study of 5,000 tweets revealed that people were sharing information, voicing concerns, and encouraging involvement, indicating a rise in engagement. Nayomi Kankanamge et al. [12] investigated the use of social networking sites, particularly Twitter, to assess disaster severity during the 2010–2011 South East Queensland Floods. They emphasized the need to combine social media data with conventional disaster management strategies for better situational awareness and reaction. Milad Mirbabaie et al. [13] investigated how crisis communication and decision-making are impacted by sense-giving on Twitter. Using a dataset of 9.4 million tweets on Hurricane Harvey, the study used social network and content analysis. The results showed that authoritative sources like governmental organizations and media outlets had a big impact on public sense-making, whereas trusted users were crucial in forming crisis narratives. The study also showed that social media may spread false

information as well as true information, making crisis communication tactics more difficult. Melissa Roy et al. [14] investigated how blame was assigned by social media users during the Ebola outbreak. The results showed that the responsibility transferred from the afflicted communities to the national governments as the disease expanded. Themes of blame were also used to border control and immigration. This change mirrored consumers' increasing view of Ebola as a regional danger connected to preexisting social and political resentment. Norizzati Azudin et al. [15] investigated the usage of Twitter by the Saudi Ministry of Health for crisis communication during COVID-19. The outcomes showed that the Saudi government successfully used Twitter to disseminate case updates, travel warnings, and preventive actions, guaranteeing prompt information delivery. The Ministry's regular tweeting—an average of six to nine tweets per day—was essential in raising public awareness and encouraging adherence to preventive measures. This preemptive strategy showed how social media may effectively manage public information amid medical emergencies. Fang Wan et al. [16] investigated how public participation in environmental policy objectives is affected by government social media accounts (GSMAs). The outcomes showed that the value of the information supplied had a bigger impact on public participation than the amount of information. The study underlined that direct communication techniques enhanced public engagement, such as accounts devoted to certain subjects and regular posting schedules. The findings emphasize how crucial it is to provide high-quality, pertinent information to successfully advance policy objectives and increase public participation. Tapio Vepsäläinen et al. [17] explored the influence of Twitter followers and Facebook likes on election results, emphasizing candidates' political backgrounds. The results demonstrated a positive correlation between election success and both Twitter followers and Facebook likes, but a higher correlation with Facebook likes. Furthermore, candidates with less political experience benefited more electorally from their social media presence than did more seasoned politicians, suggesting that social media is a more useful instrument for up-and-coming candidates to communicate. Khulekani Yakobi et al. [18] noted the key challenges associated with using social networking sites Big Data for citizen e-participation. The results identified data, process, and management as the three main difficulty categories. The 7 Vs of Big Data (volume, velocity,

variety, variability, veracity, visualization, and value) were among the data problems. The study underlined the necessity of better instruments and approaches to deal with these issues to increase public participation in governmental procedures. Woyopwa Shem et al. [19] investigated the impact of social networking sites in influencing political decision-making in Nigeria's multicultural society. Social media platforms greatly influence political discourse, improve voter mobilization, and encourage inclusive involvement, according to the research. It was discovered that social media was essential for campaign participation and election monitoring, especially among younger audiences. The report did, however, also draw attention to issues that Nigerian democratic processes face, such as the proliferation of hate speech, fake news, and disinformation. Mehul Rathi et al. [20] explored the importance of social networking sites on political decision-making, specifically in Kolkata, India. The outcomes showed that social networking sites has a big influence on how people establish political opinions, especially those who use social media regularly. The study also emphasized how social media may spread fear and anger and frequently spread false political information, which can affect voter attitudes and behavior. Oguchi Onyeizu Ajaegbu et al. [21] identified the social media's impact on political involvement and regional government. According to the research, social media is essential for igniting demonstrations, elevating popular opinions, and opposing authoritarian governments. According to the study, social networking sites like Facebook and Twitter have made it possible for people to get more involved in civic life, particularly young people, which has raised political consciousness. Nadia Sha et al. [22] surveyed how social media has transformed government operations. The results demonstrated how social media facilitates real-time communication between citizens and authorities, improving public involvement, government transparency, and crisis communication. The study also underlined how social media enhances cross-border information flow, which promotes international cooperation and aids diplomacy. Kayla Schwoerer [11] examined how Twitter users mobilized around planned changes to the Freedom of Information Act regulations in the United States. The results showed that Twitter activity significantly increased after the new regulation was announced, with people actively exchanging information, voicing their thoughts, and promoting public involvement. According to the report, Twitter was used by people and advocacy

organizations to raise awareness of the rule change and to offer instructions on how to submit public comments. Achmad Nurmandi et al. [23] surveyed the impact of social networking sites on influencing public policy processes. The findings demonstrated that social media considerably promotes policymaking by increasing data collection, opinion tracking, and public participation. Social media also assists in finding hot subjects, monitoring sensitive situations, and assessing public opinion patterns. The study underlined how social media platforms may facilitate quicker decision-making in governance and encourage openness. Hanchen Jiang and Xiao Tang [24] examined the effect of local government social media posts on citizen behavior during the COVID-19 pandemic. The results showed that citizen compliance was much increased by government social media posts, especially those that highlighted preventative actions. The study also discovered that this impact was more pronounced in places with more internet access, better-educated residents, and higher GDP per capita, underscoring the importance of socioeconomic considerations in boosting the efficacy of social media communication in times of crisis. Marlan Hutahaean et al. [25] surveyed the factors influencing e-government participation in Indonesia. The results showed that the main factor influencing citizen involvement is faith in e-government. The quality of the information, the perceived usability, and the perceived utility of e-government services posted on social media are important elements that contribute to this trust. Additionally, public trust is greatly increased when the government is transparent. Keshav Kapur and Rajitha Harikrishnan [26] directed a comparative analysis of different sentiment analysis techniques applied to data from Twitter and Reddit. The results showed that the BiLSTM model outperformed other approaches and obtained the greatest accuracy of 89.63%. The accuracy of the Naive Bayes classifier was 69.68%, while the TextBlob + Random Forest model came in second with 81.59%. The findings demonstrated that, in contrast to lexicon-based and conventional machine learning techniques, deep learning models such as BiLSTM efficiently absorb contextual meaning, improving sentiment classification performance. Paul Aondover Igbashangev et al. [27] examined the effect of social networking sites on promoting democratic practices and good governance in Nigeria. According to the findings, social media played a major role in election monitoring, whistleblowing, and the spread of reliable information. By revealing cases of bribery and

corruption, social media sites like Facebook and Twitter were essential in holding public officials responsible. The paper claims that social media platforms provide a venue for individuals to openly voice their grievances and reveal political misconduct, ultimately leading to better governance practices. Abubakar S. Yushau Alfakoro et al. [28] examined the role of social networking sites in enhancing governance in Nigeria. The results presented that social networking sites have a major role in raising public awareness, encouraging citizen involvement, and fostering consensus in government. According to the report, social media platforms have improved responsiveness, accountability, and transparency by making it easier for people to keep an eye on what the government is doing. Divine M. Keith [29] explored the effect of social networking sites on political activism. The results showed that social media greatly increases the velocity and scope of activism. Social media has given activists the ability to plan demonstrations more effectively, spread awareness, and rally support for important causes by facilitating instantaneous information exchange, real-time communication, and dynamic organizing. The study highlighted that online campaigns that are properly coordinated with physical activities increase the success of social media-driven activism, proving that digital platforms are most effective when used as a tool to magnify larger political movements rather than as a stand-alone remedy. Mohammed B.E. Saaida and Mahmoud A.M. Alhouseini [30] examined the multifaceted effect of social networking sites on political processes worldwide. The results showed that social networking greatly influences public involvement, improves citizen mobilization, and alters political discourse. People may now actively participate in political movements, add to policy discussions, and demand government accountability thanks to social networking sites like Facebook and Twitter. The authors underlined the necessity of sensible laws that reduce the dangers of social media in international politics while fostering democratic ideals, media literacy, and civic engagement. Francisca Sassetti [31] investigated the impact of crowdsourced election monitoring on Nigerian election transparency. By boosting public involvement, enabling real-time event reporting, and raising electoral bodies' accountability, the results showed that crowdsourcing increased election transparency. According to the report, there has been a discernible increase in election transparency indicators since crowdsourced election monitoring was implemented for Nigeria's

general elections in 2011 and 2015. The study underlined that although crowdsourcing can strengthen voting integrity and encourage participatory democracy, its effectiveness mostly depends on voters' digital literacy and active civil society participation. Table 1 summarizes the social media's role in government policy-making related works.

Table 1: An Overview of Social Media's Function In Government Policy-Making

Ref. No.	Year	Objective	Methodology	Dataset Used	Key Findings	Limitations
9	2022	To analyze the influence of Twitter in political decision-making, specifically in choosing a running mate	Social network analysis and semantic analysis	Twitter Dataset	Twitter plays a crucial role in shaping political decisions and public perception	Limited to Twitter; ignores other social media platforms' influence
1	2019	To provide a framework for semantic analysis that would help government policymakers make sense of social media data.	Latent Semantic Analysis	Facebook posts	Policymakers can receive real-time feedback via social media.	Limited dataset from one Facebook page. False or misleading posts are not filtered.
32	2022	To assess how social media enhances public participation in policymaking	Traditional Approach	Twitter Dataset	Social media platforms serve as an effective medium for citizen engagement in e-rulemaking	Limited dataset; does not assess long-term policy impacts
12	2019	Evaluate Twitter's ability to determine the areas affected and the severity of disasters.	Traditional Approach	Twitter Dataset	Twitter captures real-time disaster severity. Geo-tagged tweets map high-impact zones. Social media supports disaster monitoring and response.	Only uses tweets that have been geotagged. Misinformation risk. Potential gaps in geographic data.
13	2020	Analyze how sense-giving affects decision-making Twitter and communication during crises.	Traditional Approach	9,414,463 tweets	Trusted users shape crisis narratives. Sense-making is driven by authorities. False and factual information are shared on social media.	Risks of misinformation. The exclusive focus is on statistics from Twitter. The findings might not apply to every crisis.
15	2023	Analyze the usage of Twitter by the Saudi Ministry of Health to communicate during the COVID-19 situation.	Traditional Approach	Twitter Dataset	Twitter spread travel warnings, case updates, and preventative strategies. Social media helped handle crises and raise public awareness.	Restricted to one month's worth of data and Twitter.

19	2023	Examine the ways in which social media affects political choices in the multicultural nation of Nigeria.	Traditional Approach	secondary data	Social media influences political decisions, raises awareness, and mobilizes voters.	Challenges: fake news, hate speech, and bias; unregulated content fuels misinformation.
20	2021	Examine the effects of social media on political choices and investigate any connections to demographic variables.	Logistic Regression	Social media	Social media influences ideas, awareness, and trust; age and gender have an impact on participation and voting.	The whole focus is on urban Kolkata. Restricted to data from a single time frame.
22	2023	Examine the ways in which social media impacts government operations with an emphasis on openness, participation from the public, and crisis communication.	Traditional Approach	Social media	Global diplomacy, policymaking, and transparency are all improved by social media.	Insufficient attention to regional variations mostly makes use of secondary data.
23	2023	Analyze the role of social media on public policymaking by doing a meta-analysis of research from 2010 to 2020.	Traditional Approach	Social media	Social media facilitates public participation, data collection, and opinion tracking.	Lacks real-time data analysis and concentrates on published studies.
27	2023	Examine how social media might help advance democracy and responsible leadership in Nigeria.	Traditional Approach	Social media	Social media facilitates information sharing, election monitoring, and whistleblowing.	Limits more comprehensive insights by concentrating primarily on Benue State. Self-reported data is used, which might cause bias.

Several studies have explored the use of social media for understanding public opinion and informing policy decisions. For example, [9] employed social network analysis to study political decision-making, while [1] used semantic analysis on Facebook posts to provide real-time feedback to policymakers. Others like [32], [13], and [22] have demonstrated social media's role in crisis communication, disaster tracking, and e-governance. However, most of these studies use traditional analytical approaches, rely on limited or platform-specific datasets, and do not leverage machine learning for sentiment classification.

Furthermore, few studies have focused specifically on COVID-19 vaccination-related

discourse, and even fewer link sentiment analysis directly to government decision-making. This gap in real-time, data-driven public opinion analysis forms the basis for the current research.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a data-driven approach to examine public opinion toward the COVID-19 vaccine by fusing machine learning and social media analytics. The methodological framework includes four major stages: data collection, data preprocessing and annotation, feature extraction, and model development and evaluation.

3.1 Data Collection

We used the dataset to examine the significance of social networking analytics in government policymaking and decision-making. The selection of this dataset was based on its applicability to public health discussions, especially those about the COVID-19 vaccine, which were crucial in the formulation of public policy during the epidemic. Twitter data was chosen as the main source for this study for several important reasons: public accessibility, policy-relevant discussions, hashtag and trend utilization, and rich metadata. The following actions were taken as part of the data collection process:

- ✓ Keyword and Hashtag Filtering: To extract relevant tweets, keywords including "vaccine," "COVID-19 vaccine," "Pfizer," "Moderna," and associated hashtags like #GetVaccinated and #VaccineRollout were used.
- ✓ Timeframe Selection: Data was gathered at the vaccine rollout's pivotal stages in order to assess public opinion at important policy turning points.

3.2 Dataset Description

The Vaccination_all_tweets DataSet allows for thorough examination of trends in public opinion by including tweet content, user data, engagement metrics, and timestamps.

3.3 Data Preparation

Following data collection, a comprehensive preparation process was carried out to ensure the dataset's superiority and appropriateness for analysis. The steps include:

3.3.1 Data filtering process

To guarantee data quality, the dataset was subjected to a systematic filtering process:

- ✓ Initial Dataset: The dataset originally contained 228,207 rows.
- ✓ Duplicate Removal: Removing duplicates reduced the count to 228,192 rows.
- ✓ Location Filtering: Filtering for tweets related to India resulted in 45,077 rows.
- ✓ Sentiment Labeling: A subset of 8,000 rows was labeled as positive (0) and negative (1).
- ✓ Missing Values Removal: After eliminating missing values, 7,959 rows remained.

- ✓ Further Deduplication: The dataset was refined to 7,581 rows.

- ✓ Final Cleaning: A subsequent check for duplicates and null values resulted in 7,572 rows.

3.3.2 Text cleaning process

The text data was processed through multiple steps to enhance quality:

- ✓ Non-text entries were replaced with empty strings.
- ✓ Text was converted to lowercase for consistency.
- ✓ Content within brackets, URLs, HTML tags, punctuation, and unwanted special characters was removed.
- ✓ Numeric values, extra spaces, and line breaks were eliminated.
- ✓ Text was tokenized, and stopwords were removed to improve analytical focus.
- ✓ Rows with missing values in essential columns were dropped, resulting in 7,568 cleaned rows.

3.4 Annotation

Annotation is the process of adding details to collected data or a document. Here, the annotation process involves labeling the tweet text to build a dataset for sentiment analysis. To choose which texts will be annotated, the article employs a straightforward random sampling approach. The researcher's instructions carry out the annotation. There are at least four annotators who carry out the labeling.

4. PROPOSED SENTIMENT ANALYSIS STRUCTURE

Figure 2 illustrates the suggested architecture for classifying Twitter text messages as either positive or negative. After receiving textual data as input, it pre-processes it according to the language's characteristics. This includes tokenization, normalization, and the removal of punctuation, among other fundamental pre-processing steps. TF-IDF is then used in feature extraction to extract the feature. An essential feature vector (training data) of the dataset used to train the model is the task's output. After feature

extraction, the model is trained using Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest, Extra Trees, AdaBoost, Gradient Boosting, Bagging, XGBoost, MLP Classifier, and SVM machine learning algorithms. Following the evaluation of the resultant models, the optimal analysis model is

chosen based on performance analysis. A prototype that can accept English tweet messages as input and categorize the input based on whether it includes positive or negative sentiment is developed using the final model that was chosen.

Figure 2: Sentiment Analysis Structure

4.1. Preprocessing Of Proposed English Tweet Text

The goal of pre-processing English tweet messages is to get the data ready for model testing and training. It is carried out using a fundamental

text processing methods, including normalization, tokenization, and the removal of punctuation, superfluous spaces, and special characters. Refer to Figure 3.

Figure 3: Dataset Preprocessing Stages

4.1.1. Eliminating unnecessary characters and punctuation symbols

In text-based applications, data analysis, and natural language processing (NLP), text cleaning—the removal of unnecessary letters, punctuation, and symbols—is a crucial

preprocessing step. Text data frequently includes extraneous special characters, such as symbols, emojis, or punctuation, which might not be useful for analyzing the text. The source code for cleaning is in Algorithm 1, given below in Table 2.

Table 2: Cleaning Algorithm of the Dataset

<p>Algorithm 1: Cleanup vaccination all tweets DataSet.</p> <p>Input: Text in a dataset</p> <p>Output: Clean text</p> <p>Begin:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Read the text in the dataset; 2. While (! end of the text in a dataset): <p>If text is not a string, then return an empty string for non-string values;</p> <p>If the text contains URLs, then remove URLs;</p> <p>If the text contains special characters (e.g., a®ªà®•à®µà®©à®•à®•à®® à®...à®°,Ã Â®Â~Ã Â®Â°Ã Â®â€¡;Ã Â®Â~Ã Â®Â°) then Remove special characters ;</p> <p>If the text contains symbol [<>«»=-'~_ /] then Replace symbol and add space;</p> <p>If a text contains punctuation, then remove punctuation.</p> <p>If text contains a number [0-9], then remove number;</p> <p>If a text contains HTML Tags, then remove HTML tags;</p> <p>If a text contains extra white space, then trim the text;</p> <p>If the text contains stopwords, then remove stopwords;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Return clean text; <p>End:</p>

4.1.2. Tokenization

Tokenization, a crucial preprocessing step in analyzing an English Twitter dataset, breaks text up into fragments, such as words or phrases, to speed up processing. Since tweets are informal and frequently contain slang, hashtags, emoticons, special characters, and acronyms, efficient tokenization is essential to glean valuable information. This is significant because the relationships between words in a text often determine its meaning, which aids feature extraction techniques in obtaining the right structures from the dataset.

4.2. Proposed Feature Extractions

To improve classification performance, the proposed feature extraction procedure locates and extracts important statistical and linguistic features from the dataset. Figure 4 shows how this procedure works with the pre-processed and tokenized dataset. The extracted structures are then utilized for training machine learning models to

classify tweet texts into two categories: positive sentiments and negative sentiments. Here, to obtain effective feature representation, a well-established text mining algorithm, Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF), is applied [33]. The machine learning classifier is trained using feature vectors that are provided by each approach.

Figure 4: The Flow Chart For Feature Extraction

4.2.1 Feature extraction using TF-IDF

Through TF-IDF feature extraction operations, the TF is used to determine the frequency of words in the dataset. By measuring the term's IDF within the dataset, the significance of the word is conveyed. The classifiers for a word's relevance and frequency in the dataset are provided by this featured model as a feature vector for training. In this work, feature extraction is carried out by using the TF-IDF approach.

4.3. Developing Machine Learning Models

Creating machine learning models for sentiment analysis of Twitter text is essential to correctly categorizing tweets into various sentiment groups. Because social media language is informal and loud, choosing the right models is vital for efficient categorization. A variety of machine learning models are examined here, including standard classifiers like Decision Trees and Logistic Regression, as well as ensemble techniques like Random Forest, XGBoost, and boosting algorithms. This study builds a classification model by using the machine-learning algorithms Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest, Extra Trees, AdaBoost, Gradient Boosting, Bagging, XGBoost, MLP Classifier, and

SVM on the dataset features and labels, as shown in Figure 5. The goal of the modeling procedure is to use machine learning algorithms to identify patterns in the training dataset that translate the tweet texts with their attributes to the target class. A trained

model that can be used for both positive and negative sentiment analysis and prediction on newly input tweets is the result of machine learning modeling.

Figure 5: The Flow Chart For Developing The Model

4.4. Model Assessment And Testing

To assess the performance of the models, the following evaluation metrics were used:

Accuracy: Evaluates the model's overall prediction accuracy.

Precision: Evaluates the amount of correctly predicted positive cases among all predicted positives.

Recall: Assesses the ability of the model to identify actual positive cases.

F1-score: Balances these measures by offering a harmonic mean of recall and accuracy.

5. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

A personal computer with an Intel® Core™ i5-4310M processor, 2.70GHz, 2 Core(s), 8 GB of physical memory, and a 465 GB hard disk storage capacity is used to run the tools described in the preceding section. The 64-bit version of Windows 10 Pro is the OS.

5.1. Description Of The Dataset

The authors manually gathered information from Twitter to create the dataset for this work. The study's dataset is made up of tweets about the COVID-19 vaccine. After eliminating duplicates, the dataset's original 228,207 rows were downsized to 228,192. The dataset was narrowed down to 45,077 rows by filtering solely for Indian tweets, in order to focus on sentiment specific to the region. 8000 tweets were classified as either positive (labeled as 0) or negative (labeled as 1)

after the data was tagged for sentiment classification. The dataset was reduced to 7,959 rows by using further preprocessing methods, such as removing missing values. The count dropped to 7,581 when further duplicates were eliminated from the labeled dataset. A thorough text cleaning process was then applied to the dataset, which included removing non-string values, converting it to lowercase, removing text enclosed in brackets, removing URLs, HTML elements, punctuation, newlines, digits, unnecessary spaces, and undesired special characters. After tokenization, stopwords were eliminated to make sure that only significant words remained for analysis. 7,568 rows were included in the final cleaned dataset following these preparation processes. According to the class distribution, 20.14% of tweets were categorized as negative and 79.86% as positive.

5.2. Preprocessing Implementation

The authors choose which tweet text would be annotated using a straightforward random sample approach. The text messages were labeled by all four of the annotators using the same set of rules. Three of the annotators were given 1800 text messages. The fourth annotator was the researcher who oversaw the whole process of the annotation and annotated 2162 text messages. The annotation process resulted in a distribution of classes shown in Table 3 for each Annotator. The resulting two-class distribution in the dataset is shown in Table 4.

Table 3: The Annotation Of Distinct Twitter Text Messages

Label	Annotator 1	Annotator 2	Annotator 3	Annotator 4	Total Unique Annotated
Positive (0)	1452	1378	1542	1607	5979
Negative(1)	348	422	258	555	1589
Total Annotated	1800	1800	1800	2162	7562

Table 4: The Dataset's Two-Class Distribution

Label Or Class	Number of tweet text messages
Positive	5979
Negative	1589
Total	7562

The pairwise agreement analysis among annotators reveals varying levels of consistency in sentiment classification. The highest agreement is observed between Annotator 1 and Annotator 2 with 95.89%,

followed closely by Annotator 1 and Annotator 3 with 95.00%. However, the lowest agreement scores involve Annotator 4, with the agreement percentages between Annotator 4 and the other annotators ranging around 90.86%.

5.3. Results And Discussion

Several machine learning models were used to accomplish sentiment analysis on social media data in order to assess how well they classified sentiments for use in government decision-making. The models considered include Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest, Extra Trees, AdaBoost, Gradient Boosting, Bagging, XGBoost, MLP Classifier, and Support Vector Machine (SVM). Their performance was assessed based on accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

5.3.1 Model performance analysis

The classification models were evaluated on a Twitter sentiment analysis dataset, with performance measured using Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-score. The performance analysis of many machine learning models in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score is displayed in Table 5.

Table 5: Analysis Of Different ML Models' Performance

Classification Models	Logistic Regression	Decision Tree	Random Forest	Extra Trees	AdaBoost	Gradient Boosting	Bagging	XGBoost	MLP Classifier	SVM
Accuracy	0.81	0.74	0.79	0.79	0.81	0.81	0.79	0.80	0.71	0.81
Precision	0.77	0.72	0.70	0.72	0.85	0.75	0.72	0.72	0.72	0.76
Recall	0.81	0.74	0.79	0.79	0.81	0.81	0.79	0.80	0.71	0.81
F1-score	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.74	0.73	0.73	0.74	0.74	0.71	0.73

Figure 6: ML Model Performance Comparison

From the comparative analysis of classification models as shown in Figure 6, the Logistic Regression, AdaBoost, Gradient Boosting, and SVM achieved the highest accuracy of 81.10%. Random Forest and Bagging showed moderate performance with accuracy values of 79.39% and 79.32%, respectively. The Decision Tree classifier exhibited the lowest accuracy of 74.24%, indicating that it was more prone to overfitting and misclassification. Precision values varied across models, with AdaBoost achieving the highest precision of 84.63%, followed by Logistic Regression with 77.16% and SVM with 76.13%. The Decision Tree model had the lowest precision of 72.28%, reflecting a higher false positive rate. The recall values followed a similar pattern as accuracy, with Logistic Regression, AdaBoost, Gradient Boosting, and SVM achieving the highest recall scores with 81.10%. The F1-score values, which balance precision and recall, indicated that Bagging with 74.05%, Extra Trees with 73.93%, and XGBoost with 73.56% provided competitive performance alongside the top-performing models. The high recall scores across most models indicate that the classifiers are effective in identifying sentiment categories correctly.

5.3.2 Confusion matrix perspectives

The confusion matrix breaks out attitudes that were properly and erroneously identified, revealing the advantages and disadvantages of each approach. By examining false positives and false negatives, we can assess the reliability of a model in accurately detecting positive and negative sentiments. This analysis is particularly crucial for government decision-making, where misclassification of sentiments could lead to incorrect policy interpretations. The confusion matrices for each model were analyzed to understand misclassification trends. Logistic Regression and AdaBoost had the fewest false positives and false negatives, making them reliable choices for sentiment classification. In contrast, the Decision Tree and MLP Classifier exhibited higher misclassification rates, with a significant number of false negatives, suggesting that these models struggled with correctly identifying negative sentiments. The ensemble methods, such as Random Forest and XGBoost demonstrated balanced performance by reducing both false

positives and false negatives compared to single classifiers like Decision Tree presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Confusion Matrix Of Various ML Models

5.4 Discussion

The results indicate that ensemble learning techniques such as AdaBoost, Gradient Boosting, and XGBoost perform well in sentiment classification tasks, offering high accuracy and balanced precision-recall trade-offs. These models can be effectively utilized by government agencies to analyze public sentiment on various policies, social issues, and governance initiatives. A crucial observation is that models with higher recall are preferable in decision-making scenarios where detecting negative sentiments is vital. For instance, in policymaking, a misclassification of negative sentiment as positive could lead to flawed decisions. Therefore, a hybrid approach combining AdaBoost and Logistic Regression can be considered to maximize accuracy while ensuring minimal false negatives.

6. CONCLUSION

The study's conclusions demonstrate how well machine learning models analyze social media sentiment for use in government decision-making. Among the models evaluated, ensemble-based techniques such as AdaBoost, Gradient Boosting, and XGBoost exhibited superior performance in terms of accuracy, recall, and F1-score, making them suitable for real-world sentiment analysis applications. The results emphasize the importance of recall in detecting negative sentiments, ensuring that government decisions are informed by accurate public opinion analysis. Overall, the paper demonstrates that machine learning models can effectively analyze social media sentiments, providing governments with valuable insights to make data-driven decisions. By leveraging high-performing classifiers, policymakers can monitor public opinions in real time, identify emerging concerns, and respond proactively to citizen feedback.

Future work should focus on incorporating deep learning models such as LSTMs, CNNs, or transformer-based architectures like BERT to improve classification accuracy and adaptability across diverse social media datasets. By integrating sentiment analysis into decision-making frameworks, governments can proactively address public concerns, enhance policy effectiveness, and strengthen citizen engagement.

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